

Synthesis of 3-Benzoyl-5-Hydroxy-2-Phenyl-4-*isogramines* and 4-Arylthiomethyl-5-Hydroxy-2-Phenylindoles

G. S. GADAGINAMATH and S. SIDDAPPA*

Department of Chemistry, Karnatak University, Dharwar-3.

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Various 1-substituted-3-benzoyl-5-hydroxy-2-phenylindoles were subjected to the Mannich reaction to obtain biologically interesting 3-benzoyl-5-hydroxy-4-*isogramines* whose structures were confirmed on the basis of PMR spectral data. The nucleophilic displacement of dimethyl amine from 3-benzoyl-4-dimethylaminomethyl-5-hydroxy-2-phenylindoles with thiophenols was thermally effected to yield the respective 3-benzoyl-4-arylthiomethyl-5-hydroxy-2-phenylindoles. The UV pattern of all these compounds is discussed with reference to that of their precursors, 3-benzoyl-5-hydroxy-2-phenylindoles.

A large number of investigations¹ pertaining to serotonin have stressed the vital role of this compound in various functions of the central nervous system. Certain mental disorders have been considered² to be originating from the disturbed serotonin level in the brain. Bonnycastle *et al.*³ have shown that the serotonin level in brain was elevated by the administration of various CNS depressants to the rats. Since, some 5-hydroxy-4-*isogramines* are reported⁴ to possess predominantly CNS stimulating action, these may prove to be potent antagonists of serotonin. Hence, in continuation of our previous work⁵, the present paper deals with 5-hydroxy-4-*isogramines* and 4-arylthiomethyl-2-phenylindoles.

5-Hydroxyindoles are reported⁶ to undergo exclusive aminomethylation adjacent to the hydroxyl group even though the C-3 position of the indole ring is vacant. Of the two *ortho*-positions (C-4 & C-6), the C-4 position is the preferred site for the entry of the aminomethyl substituent though this position is perished by C-3 H atom⁷. In our present work, when 1-substituted-3-benzoyl-5-hydroxy-2-phenylindoles were subjected to the Mannich reaction with various secondary amines, the aminomethyl substituent preferentially entered the C-4 position yielding various 4-*isogramines*, despite the presence of the bulky benzoyl substituent at C-3 position.

1-Substituted-3-benzoyl-5-hydroxy-2-phenylindoles⁸ (1-4) were subjected to the Mannich reaction by using dimethylamine, diethylamine, piperidine and morpholine to obtain the desired 3-benzoyl-5-hydroxy-2-phenyl-4-*isogramines* (5-20) in 47-64% yield. The nucleophilic displacement of dimethylamine from 3-benzoyl-4-dimethylaminomethyl-5-hydroxy-2-phenylindoles (5, 9, 13 & 17) with thiophenol, *o*-chlorothiophenol, *m*-chlorothiophenol and *p*-chlorothiophenol was thermally effected to yield the corresponding 3-benzoyl-4-phenyl(*or* chlorophenyl) thiomethyl-5-hydroxy-2-phenylindoles (21-36) in 65-75% yield.

The structure of 1-*n*-propyl-3-benzoyl-4-dimethylaminomethyl-5-hydroxy-2-phenylindole (5) (Table 1) is fully substantiated by its PMR data. The integration of aromatic region (2.16-3.55 τ) accounts for only twelve protons and this indicates that one of the thirteen aromatic protons present in its precursor (1) has been replaced by the dimethylaminomethyl group. The entry of this group into C-4 position is evident from the doublet (3.22 τ , J 8.5 Hz) attributable to the C-6 proton. The two *ortho*-protons of the C-3 benzoyl function being *ortho* to carbonyl suffered deshielding⁹ and gave

* 13, Basappa Layout, Gavipuram, Bangalore-560019.

a multiplet (2.27 τ). The C-4 dimethylaminomethyl group displayed two singlets, one at 6.33 τ (-CH₂-) and another at 7.77 τ (two N-methyls). The C-5 hydroxyl proton signal was observed at lower field (-0.33 τ) and this is attributed to the intramolecular H-bonding of this proton with the C-4 substituent. The *n*-propyl group attached to indole N showed a triplet (-N-CH₂, 6.01 τ , J 7.5 Hz), a multiplet (-CH₂-, 8.28 τ) and another triplet (-CH₃, 9.27 τ) (cf. Ref. 9).

The UV spectrum of (5) in dioxane solution shows absorption maxima at 231 (log ϵ 4.39) and 288 (4.16) nm. The long wavelength maximum (325 nm) observed in the UV spectrum of 1-*n*-propyl-3-benzoyl-5-hydroxy-2-phenylindole (1) in same solvent has shown hypsochromic shift in the spectrum of (5) (Fig. 1). The polarised form of the type (1) might be one of the

resonance hybrids responsible for the long wavelength band (325 nm). Szmuszkovicz¹⁰ has recorded the UV spectra of 1-methyl-3-benzoylindole (37) (317 nm, log ϵ 4.205) and 1-methyl-2-phenyl-3-benzoylindole (38) (325 nm, log ϵ 3.997) in 95% ethanol and it is to be noted that the extinction coefficient (log ϵ 3.997) of (38) is less than that of (37) (log ϵ 4.205) which might be due to the possible steric hindrance of C-2 phenyl. Similarly, the UV spectra of *trans*-stilbene derivatives have been reported¹¹ to show reduction in maximum extinction and also the hypsochromic shift of long wavelength band when the substituents at the *ortho*-positions caused steric hindrance to the planarity of molecule. Thus, in case of compound (5), the steric hindrance caused to the C-3 benzoyl function by the C-4 dimethylaminomethyl group in addition to the steric effect of C-2 phenyl, might have further distorted the co-planarity of this C-3 benzoyl with rest of the indole moiety and hence, the long wavelength band (325 nm) is absent in the UV spectrum of (5).

The UV spectrum of 1-*n*-propyl-3-benzoyl-4-phenylthiomethyl-5-hydroxy-2-phenylindole (21) in dioxane shows absorption maxima at 230 and 287 nm (Fig. 1). The IR spectra of the thioethers (21-36) were recorded and show bands for chelated hydroxyl (3250-3330 cm⁻¹) and ketonic (1605-1615 cm⁻¹) functions.

The 4-*isogramines* (5-20) were screened for their anti 5-HT and antimicrobial activities and some of them were found active¹². The 4-thioethers (21-36) were tested^{12a} for their antimicrobial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* and were found to be less active.

Fig. 1. Absorption Spectra

Experimental

The 1-substituted-3-benzoyl-5-hydroxy-2-phenylindoles (1-4) were prepared as described earlier.⁸

1-*n*-Propyl-3-benzoyl-4-dimethylaminomethyl-5-hydroxy-2-phenylindole (5): A solution of 1-*n*-propyl-3-benzoyl-5-hydroxy-2-phenylindole (1) (1.065 g., 0.003 mole) in dioxane (10 ml) was added to a cooled, stirred mixture of dimethylamine (30%, 0.75 g., 0.006 mole) and formaldehyde (37%, 0.4g, 0.003 mole) in glacial acetic (1 ml). On adding acetic acid (1 ml) to the reaction mixture, it was heated to 90° for 10-15 min. and then left at room temperature for 24hr. It was poured into ice cold water, the suspended particles were removed by filtration and the filtrate was made alkaline with ammonia solution (15%). The separated 4-*isogramine* (5) was extracted with ether and the residue obtained on removing ether was crystallised from aqueous alcohol.

Various 4-*isogramines* (5-20) and their hydrochlorides prepared from the hydroxyindoles (1-4) using dimethylamine, diethylamine, piperidine and morpholine by following the above procedure are described in Table 1.

1-*n*-Propyl-3-benzoyl-4-phenylthiomethyl-5-hydroxy-2-phenylindole (21): 1-*n*-Propyl-3-benzoyl-4-dimethylaminomethyl-5-hydroxy-2-phenylindole (5) (0.412 g., 0.001 mole) and thiophenol (0.11 g., 0.001 mole) were intimately mixed and heated in an oil bath at 150°-155° until the evolution of dimethylamine ceased (about 0.5 hr). It was cooled, extracted with benzene and the residue obtained on removing benzene under suction was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether to get pure 4-*thioether* (21).

TABLE I—SUBSTITUTED-3-BENZOYL-5-HYDROXY-2-PHENYL-4-ISOGRAMINES (5-20)

Comp- ound	1-Substi- tuent R	4-Substi- tuent	M.P. °C	Found %	Formula	Requires %	UV spectra dioxane $\lambda_{\max}$ nm (log ϵ)	PMR* spectral data τ
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
5	<i>n</i> -Propyl	Dimethyl- amino	138	C, 78.81 H, 7.07 N, 6.83	$C_{27}H_{30}N_2O_2$	C, 78.63 H, 6.80 N, 6.80	231(4.39) 288(4.16)	9.27, 8.28 and 6.01 (-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -CH ₂ , t, m & t, J 7.5); 7.77(-N (CH ₃) ₂ , s); 6.33 (-CH ₂ - N, s); 2.16-3.33(ArH, 12H, m); 3.22(C-6 H, d, J 8.5); -0.33br(C-5 OH, s); 2.27 (<i>o</i> -H of C-3 COPh, m).
5.HCl	"	"	150(d)	N, 6.20	$C_{27}H_{29}N_2O_2Cl$	N, 6.25	—	—
6.HCl	"	Diethyl- amino	76(d)	N, 6.00	$C_{29}H_{32}N_2O_2Cl$	N, 5.88	—	—
7	"	Piperidino	149	C, 80.07 H, 7.29 N, 6.22	$C_{30}H_{32}N_2O_2$	C, 79.84 H, 7.08 N, 6.20	—	—
7.HCl	<i>n</i> -Propyl	Piperidino	161(d)	N, 5.83	$C_{30}H_{31}N_2O_2Cl$	N, 5.74	—	—
8.HCl	"	Morpholino	152(d)	N, 5.54	$C_{29}H_{31}N_2O_2Cl$	N, 5.72	—	—
9	<i>n</i> -Butyl	Dimethyl- amino	130	C, 78.94 H, 6.86 N, 6.71	$C_{28}H_{30}N_2O_2$	C, 78.86 H, 7.04 N, 6.57	229(4.42) 289(4.18)	9.25, 8.17-9.03 & 6.02 (butyl, deformed t, m & t, J 7.5); 7.78 (-N(CH ₃) ₂ , s); 6.35 (-CH ₂ -N, s); 2.2-3.4 (ArH, m); 3.3(C-6 H, d, J 9); -0.83br (C-5 OH, s); 2.36(<i>o</i> -H of C-3 benzoyl, m).
9.HCl	"	"	160(d)	N, 6.32	$C_{28}H_{29}N_2O_2Cl$	N, 6.06	—	—
10.HCl	"	Diethyl- amino	120(d)	N, 5.87	$C_{30}H_{32}N_2O_2Cl$	N, 5.72	—	—
11.HCl	"	Piperidino	76(d)	N, 5.40	$C_{31}H_{33}N_2O_2Cl$	N, 5.58	—	—
12.HCl	"	Morpholino	161(d)	N, 5.34	$C_{30}H_{32}N_2O_2Cl$	N, 5.56	—	—
13	<i>iso</i> -Butyl	Dimethyl- amino	141	C, 78.62 H, 7.25 N, 6.50	$C_{28}H_{30}N_2O_2$	C, 78.86 H, 7.04 N, 6.57	230(4.44) 290(4.19)	9.34, 8.13 & 6.15 (<i>iso</i> - Butyl, d, m & d, J 7); 7.8(-N(CH ₃) ₂ , s); 6.38 (-CH ₂ -N, s); 2.3-3.46 (ArH, m); 3.32(C-6 H, d, J 8.5); 0.7br(C-5 OH, s); 2.4(<i>o</i> -H of C-3 COPh, m).
13.HCl	"	"	210(d)	N, 6.12	$C_{28}H_{29}N_2O_2Cl$	N, 6.06	—	—
14.HCl	"	Diethyl- amino	155(d)	N, 5.80	$C_{30}H_{32}N_2O_2Cl$	N, 5.72	—	—
15	"	Piperidino	146	C, 80.02 H, 7.09 N, 6.04	$C_{31}H_{34}N_2O_2$	C, 79.82 H, 7.30 N, 6.01	—	—
15.HCl	"	"	210(d)	N, 5.47	$C_{31}H_{33}N_2O_2Cl$	N, 5.58	—	—
16	"	Morpholino	138	C, 76.98 H, 6.8 N, 6.01	$C_{30}H_{32}N_2O_2$	C, 77.11 H, 6.84 N, 5.98	—	—
16.HCl	"	"	205(d)	N, 5.51	$C_{30}H_{31}N_2O_2Cl$	N, 5.56	—	—
17	Benzyl	Dimethyl- amino	175	C, 81.00 H, 5.78 N, 6.14	$C_{31}H_{32}N_2O_2$	C, 80.76 H, 6.08 N, 6.08	229(4.42) 290(4.15)	7.75(-N(CH ₃) ₂ , s); 6.3 (-CH ₂ -N, s); 4.75 (-CH ₂ -Ph, s); 2.1-3.37 (ArH, m); 3.28(C-6 H, d, J 7); 0.73 br (C-5 OH, s); 2.25 (<i>o</i> -H of C-3 COPh, m).
17.HCl	"	"	143(d)	N, 5.53	$C_{31}H_{31}N_2O_2Cl$	N, 5.65	—	—
18.HCl	"	Diethyl- amino	75(d)	N, 5.41	$C_{30}H_{32}N_2O_2Cl$	N, 5.34	—	—
19	"	Piperidino	172	C, 81.42 H, 6.52 N, 5.74	$C_{34}H_{32}N_2O_2$	C, 81.60 H, 6.40 N, 5.60	—	—
19.HCl	"	"	167(d)	N, 5.33	$C_{34}H_{31}N_2O_2Cl$	N, 5.22	—	—
20	"	Morpholino	164	C, 78.69 H, 6.03 N, 5.53	$C_{33}H_{30}N_2O_2$	C, 78.89 H, 5.98 N, 5.58	—	—
20.HCl	"	"	220(d)	N, 5.12	$C_{33}H_{29}N_2O_2Cl$	N, 5.21	—	—

* The PMR spectra were recorded on Varian T 60 MHz NMR spectrometer in CDCl₃ solutions using TMS as an internal standard; J values are in Hz; br, broadened; s, singlet; d, doublet; t, triplet; m, multiplet.

Various 4-arylthiomethyl ethers (21-36) prepared by heating the 4-isogramines (5, 9, 13 & 17) with thiophenol, *o*-chlorothiophenol, *m*-chlorothiophenol and *p*-chlorothiophenol are described in Table 2.

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TABLE 2—1-SUBSTITUTED-3-BENZOYL-4-ARYLTHIOMETHYL-5-HYDROXY-2-PHENYLINDOLES (21-36)

Comp-ound.	1-Substi-tuent R	4-Substi-tuent R ₂	M. P. °C	TLC* (R _f value)	Found %	Formula	Requires %	UV Spectra dioxane λ _{max} nm (log ε)	IR spectra** Nujol ν OH	ν C=O
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
21	<i>n</i> -Propyl	Phenyl	180	0.506	C, 77.76 H, 5.90 N, 2.97	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ NO ₂ S	C, 77.98 H, 5.66 N, 2.94	230 (4.42) 287 (4.20)	3290 b	1613 s
22	"	<i>o</i> -Chloro-phenyl	189	0.518	C, 72.51 H, 5.01 N, 2.70	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ NO ₂ SCI	C, 72.73 H, 5.08 N, 2.74	230 (4.44) 282 (4.19)	3300 b	1612 s
23	"	<i>m</i> -Chloro-phenyl	168	0.566	C, 72.63 H, 5.15 N, 2.81	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ NO ₂ SCI	C, 72.73 H, 5.08 N, 2.74	288 (4.48) 290 (4.28)	3290 b	1610 s
24	"	<i>p</i> -Chloro-phenyl	210	0.542	C, 72.53 H, 4.85 N, 2.86	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ NO ₂ SCI	C, 72.73 H, 5.08 N, 2.74	230 (4.49) 290 (4.31)	3315 b	1614 s
25	<i>n</i> -Butyl	Phenyl	171	0.573	C, 77.94 H, 5.79 N, 2.96	C ₂₂ H ₂₈ NO ₂ S	C, 78.20 H, 5.91 N, 2.85	230 (4.50) 290 (4.30)	3310 b	1614 s
26	"	<i>o</i> -Chloro-phenyl	165	0.585	C, 72.98 H, 5.36 N, 2.59	C ₂₂ H ₂₈ NO ₂ SCI	C, 73.07 H, 5.33 N, 2.66	228 (4.51) 288 (4.32)	3285 b	1611 s
27	"	<i>m</i> -Chloro-phenyl	166	0.61	C, 73.28 H, 5.60 N, 2.70	C ₂₂ H ₂₈ NO ₂ SCI	C, 73.07 H, 5.33 N, 2.66	229 (4.50) 289 (4.29)	3265 b	1615 s
28	"	<i>p</i> -Chloro-phenyl	194	0.598	C, 73.26 H, 5.09 N, 2.67	C ₂₂ H ₂₈ NO ₂ SCI	C, 73.07 H, 5.33 N, 2.66	231 (4.50) 291 (4.32)	3310 b	1610 s
29	<i>iso</i> -Butyl	Phenyl	174	0.529	C, 78.12 H, 5.89 N, 2.80	C ₂₂ H ₂₈ NO ₂ S	C, 78.20 H, 5.91 N, 2.85	231 (4.54) 290 (4.37)	3290 b	1605 s
30	"	<i>o</i> -Chloro-phenyl	216	0.55	C, 73.26 H, 5.06 N, 2.68	C ₂₂ H ₂₈ NO ₂ SCI	C, 73.07 H, 5.33 N, 2.66	229 (4.45) 290 (4.28)	3330 b	1610 s
31	<i>iso</i> -Butyl	<i>m</i> -Chloro-phenyl	170	0.588	C, 72.80 H, 5.56 N, 2.67	C ₂₂ H ₂₈ NO ₂ SCI	C, 73.07 H, 5.33 N, 2.66	228 (4.47) 288 (4.25)	3260 b	1608 s
32	"	<i>p</i> -Chloro-phenyl	197	0.60	C, 73.13 H, 5.20 N, 2.73	C ₂₂ H ₂₈ NO ₂ SCI	C, 73.07 H, 5.33 N, 2.66	230 (4.47) 288 (4.31)	3260 b	1612 s
33	Benzyl	Phenyl	195	0.575	C, 80.12 H, 5.03 N, 2.70	C ₂₃ H ₂₇ NO ₂ S	C, 79.98 H, 5.14 N, 2.67	230 (4.45) 288 (4.27)	3300 b	1615 s
34	"	<i>o</i> -Chloro-phenyl	231	0.60	C, 75.23 H, 4.54 N, 2.54	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ NO ₂ SCI	C, 75.06 H, 4.65 N, 2.50	225 (4.44) 285 (4.21)	3250 b	1613 s
35	"	<i>m</i> -Chloro-phenyl	207	0.638	C, 74.90 H, 4.80 N, 2.63	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ NO ₂ SCI	C, 75.06 H, 4.65 N, 2.50	226 (4.49) 287 (4.27)	3250 b	1610 s
36	"	<i>p</i> -Chloro-phenyl	232	0.65	C, 75.16 H, 4.90 N, 2.58	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ NO ₂ SCI	C, 75.06 H, 4.65 N, 2.50	226 (4.52) 290 (4.36)	3280 b	1610 s

*Silica gel G, benzene-ethyl acetate (4 : 1). ** b, broad ; s, strong.

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